

Examining Corruptions, Insecurity and Criminal Justice Institutions in Nigeria: Implications on National Development

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the nexus between corruptions, insecurity and criminal justice institutions in Nigeria and their impact on national development. Corruption breeds insecurity and criminal justice institutions seem overwhelmed in taming these twin evils in the country which inadvertently impact gravely on national development. The myriad of insecurity- terrorism, insurgency, kidnapping, herdsmen militia, armed robbery, and sundry violent crimes have continued to haunt the country courtesy of corruption by government officials and inefficient criminal justice institutions that are also enmeshed in corruption. Despite all the hues and cry of government fighting corruption, insecurity and reforming the criminal justice institutions, corruption and insecurity have remained the most problematic issue in Nigeria. The paper relied largely on qualitative content analysis utilizing secondary sources of data collection through journal articles, books, periodicals, news prints and internet materials. The theoretical framework hinges on rational choice theory. The paper finds that the way government define problem will also determine the direction of their reaction, thus government seem to effectively define corruption, insecurity and incapacitated criminal justice institutions as acceptable frameworks of governance. Government complicity in fighting corruption and insecurity is due largely to weakened criminal justice system. The paper concludes that national development is dwarfed by the heavy burden of corruption, insecurity and inefficient and ineffective criminal justice institutions ridden also by corruption, ineptitude, and impunity. The paper recommends among others that Nigerians must take the destiny of the country in their hands and should not allow political rulers to take the country for granted. Government must be serious with governance and allow rule of law to guide its actions and institutions.

Keywords: Corruption, Insecurity, Criminal Justice, National Development

INTRODUCTION

Corruption is a global phenomenon that is deeply-rooted in every sector of the social institutions across the world with its harmful effects quite devastating. From the Europe to Asia, South America to Africa, North America to Australia and Antarctica, the menace of corruption remain the same. Ahmed (2006) noted that in this globalized society, contemporary man stands on the precipice of corruption and insecurity wallowing in agony of the twin evils as the present situation is unpalatable, murky and unpredictable. The issue of corruption and insecurity has a global perspective. The United States of America, United Kingdom, Democratic Republic of Congo, Sudan, Chad and some other countries have

been enmeshed in cases of corruption that impact on security. For example, United States dealings in Iraq in which over \$88.1 Million US Dollars was over paid in eleven projects involving oil and military contracts (Transparency International, 2008). Our society is greatly deepened and its societal fabrics destroyed to the bone marrow by the evils of corruption and insecurity. The criminal justice institutions which ought to be the societal watchdog of its values and norms is not left out in the mess. Nigeria is bedeviled by myriad of social problems as nepotism, ethno-religiosity, fraud, embezzlement, pen robbery, armed robbery, greed, indolence, poverty, unemployment, kidnapping, terrorism, cattle rustling, armed banditry, injustice, discrimination, marginalization, bribery and corruption (Eyoh, 2015), society and its institutions seem weakly incapacitated to combat these evils engulfing it.

Safeguarding the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the state is the cardinal point of Nigerian national security policy (The Library of Congress, 2014). However, the change mantra of providing security, fighting corruption and enhanced economic development which gave President Mohammadu Buhari the leeway to win in the 2015 general election have been dashed to the dogs. The crux is that increased corruption, increased insecurity cum high level of unemployment and poverty are sparkling clear in Nigeria. In terms of security, Nigeria is ranked third most risky or terrorized country in the world (The Institute for Economics and Peace, 2018). Nigeria was declared the poverty capital of the world in 2018 with about 86.9 million people (50%) of the population living in severe poverty in a report by the World Poverty Clock (Yomi, 2018). In 2020 Nigeria's poverty rate was put at 71% while it is estimated that poor people will increase by 90 million (45% of the population) in 2022 (The Conversion, 2021). As of 2023, about 25 million Nigerians were said to be at risk of hunger especially in Northern Nigeria where violence and insecurity had persisted (Madhok & English, 2023). More so, youth unemployment level have continued to soar at 55.4% (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). On the other hand, in 2021, Nigeria was ranked 154 out of 180 countries in the corruption index in the world. (Transparency International, 2021; Erezi, 2022). This shows how badly corruption has eaten deeply in the fabrics of the Nigerian society. Corruption cum security are deep seated problem that has messed effective leadership governance in Nigeria. The implication is that a failed governance begets failed state, failed state begets corrupt, insecure and weak institutions.

Various scholars Ogbuide (2012) discussed political leadership and corruption since 1960 and how it impacted on the socio-economic development of the country. Bajpai (2015) did a comparative analysis of the issues of corruption and insecurity in Nigeria and India and concluded that corruption and insecurity are the greatest problems in Nigeria. Abamara, Felix, Oguegbe (2015) examined the incidences of corruption and insecurity in Nigeria from psychological perspective. They felt that corruption and insecurity has affected the wellbeing of Nigerians. They concluded that corruption and insecurity exist because of high rate of unemployment, poverty, economic recession and advocated for equitable management of the economy. Chinnah (2020) discussed corruption and insecurity in Nigeria fourth republic. He was of the view that corruption and insecurity are by-products of bad governance and that the people who are charged with the responsibility to combat corruption and insecurity are themselves corruption ridden thereby jeopardizing the fight against insecurity. However, there remains a dearth of research on the nexus between corruption and insecurity. While most of the scholars cited above may be right in their views, none of the studies investigated corruption, insecurity and criminal justice institutions in Nigeria as been presented in this paper; most of the researches (Chinnah, 2020; Abamara, Felix & Oguegbe, 2015; Okonkwo, 2007) dealt with corruption and insecurity in the general senses, this paper intends to focus on corruption involving arms deal cum insecurity, security forces and criminal justice institutions and how the impact on the national development. It must be emphasized that criminal justice institutions play key role in instilling discipline or destroying what remains of the justice system.

Conceptual Clarification

Corruption, Insecurity and Criminal Justice Institutions

There is no single definition of corruption that is generally acceptable. Corruption itself is a broad and relative concept that has varying meanings to different persons or groups (Hao & Johnston, 2002, Wedel,

2001; Thompson, 1993). The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary defines corruption as “dishonest or illegal behaviour, especially for people in authority” (Hornby, 2000 p.261). The emphasis here is people in legal authority, people in authority who are sworn constitutionally to uphold the law and to act honestly with integrity in the exercise of their duty. It excludes corruption committed by ordinary citizens. Japhet (2014) view corruption as the abuse of entrusted power or authority for personal benefits. For the purpose of this study we will use this definition as a working concept. The fact is that corruption involve persons who hold legal positions and powers which they use to influence decisions to their personal or group interests. It is this group of persons that are of interests to us in this study especially when we are interrogating insecurity and corruption in Nigeria.

Insecurity refers to a state of uncertainty which depicts danger, harm and instability. Insecurity depicts state of unrest, disorder, uncertainty, anarchy, fear, lawlessness, and exposure to risk of being harmed, injured or killed; it is the absence of security, peace and development. Insecurity indicates that the condition of being protected against physical, emotional, psychological as well as from harm, danger or attack or terror is completely at the merciful of insidious criminals. Insecurity exposes everyone to criminal victimization without borders.

Criminal justice institutions are government agencies charged with the responsibility of administration and dispensation of justice in the society. It is regarded as any government institution or organization including other support establishments that operates in the processes of the management of crime and criminality in any society (Siegel, 2005; Reid, 2000). They are basically three components – the police, the court and correctional services; but this study will look beyond these institutions. In Nigeria, these institutions though independent of each other but interwoven and interrelated with each other in operations and justice service delivery; to the extent that one cannot do without the other in justice administration.

Literature Review

Perhaps one of the difficult task in defining corruption is its categorization. There is generally unacceptable form of categorizing corruption, this because what is corruption by one person is acceptable by another. However, attempt is made to isolate what we consider as forms of corruption. Ahmed (2006) categorized corruption as moral corruption, religious corruption, political corruption, legal corruption, financial corruption and ideological corruption. These are all found in the Nigerian society, hence Achebe (2000, p. 38) argued that “Nigerians are corrupt because the system under which they live today makes corruption easy and profitable”. Corruption is a pandemic virus in Nigerian society. This is exemplified by the news of the Accountant General of the Federation Mr. Ahmed Idris who is involved in an Eighty Billion Naira fraud (Opejobi, 2022). It seems the political elites are brazenly in competition of who takes the position of the most corrupt politician or leader in Nigeria. This is because there is no institution or leader that has what it takes to effectively prosecute corrupt political elites in Nigeria since the same leader is engrossed in the same crime. This happened within the government of President Muhammadu Buhari who rode into political victory under the tripod of anti-corruption, security and economy.

Various scholars, institutions and agencies have made attempts to categorize corruption. For example, Bolsvert, Dent, and Quraishi, (2014) categorized corruption into six namely: supply versus demand corruption, grand versus petty corruption, conventional versus unconventional corruption, public versus private corruption, systematic versus individual or isolated corruption and commission versus omission corruption.

For the purpose of this study, the following categories and explanation provided by Bolsvert et al. (2014) will suffice for our discourse. Supply versus demand corruption (also known as active or passive corruption): Supply side corruption means the act of offering an illicit payment or undue advantage whereas demand side corruption involves the acceptance or solicitation of such a payment or advantage. In Nigeria, politicians, political elites, public and civil servants are deep-necked in both supply and demand corruption because of their unique positions in the society. In budget approvals, appointments, project allocations, promotions, transfers, job placements etc., the narratives are the same in terms of the

level of corruption. Grand versus petty corruption: Grand corruption or political corruption involves persons in high ranking public office who use their privileged positions to exploit opportunities which are presented in government jobs specifically in contract awards, budget padding etc. whereas petty corruption or bureaucratic corruption refers to the involvement of public administration officials and non-elected officials. It includes bribes paid for custom officials, tax official, police officers, road safety officers and other government officials. Petty corruption is most rampant and omnipresent in every sector of the Nigerian society; it is very highly pervasive, visible and institutionalized culture among citizens of every socio-economic class. There is no segment of government institution that you enter that you will not find it rampantly displayed. Conventional versus unconventional corruption: Conventional corruption is said to occur when government official in both high and low ranking positions illegitimately receive or accumulate undue advantage for their own personal use in disregard to public interest. The violation of the 2023 electoral guidelines and processes before declaring the winner in the 2023 presidential election was a conventional corruption because whatever guise was used to declare the winner of most of the elections especially the presidential election was done in utter disregard to public interest of the generality of the Nigerian people, that impunity and display of shame of conventional corruption was displayed by the Adamawa state electoral commissioner in collaboration with security officials. On the other hand, unconventional corruption exists where a public or government official acts without consideration for public public's interest, the goal being to attain a specific and personal gain as exemplified in financial misappropriation, theft of government property, embezzlement of public funds or breach of trust etc. The lack of accountability in the money allocated to the military for the procurement of security equipment by former Chiefs of staff of the Army, Navy and Air force is a typical example of this corruption. In other to demonstrate, the helplessness of the people and the impunity of their act, President Buhari went ahead to appoint them as Nigerian's ambassadors; slapping the faces of Nigerians and rubbing them with shits and asking them to go to hell

Public versus private corruption: Public corruption involves a public official whether foreign or local whereas private corruption or private-to-private corruption involves only individuals in the private sector. Examples include bribery, swindling, mafia method (organized and corporate crimes). Systemic corruption exists where corruption is pervasive or entrenched in a society whereas individual or isolated corruption exists when corruption is rare or consists of a few individuals. Nigeria's corruption has been described severally as endemic and systemic. Systemic because it exists almost in every sector of governance and businesses; it is routine in dealings between the government and private individuals and have in fact become part and parcel of Nigerian culture. This creates tensions between formal and informal rules and they are strong incentives for public officials, businesses and individuals to comply with this illegitimate system. Those who seem to oppose it are treated as outcast and betrayals. The commission and omission corruption involves acts of corruption that can be carried out by commission or by omission. In this respect, a public official can either succumb to commit the act of corruption or refrain to act in the performance of his duties in exchange for a benefit from individuals or government or business. These outlined acts of corruption exists in varying degrees in Nigeria. In fact, the bane of national development, insecurity, poverty, unemployment and criminality in the country are deep-rooted in corruption. Corruption exacerbate insecurity especially when funds meant for the purchase of security equipment are embezzled by military officials and nobody is brought to accountability. The impunity in which people are corrupt in the country is the impunity terrorists and kidnappers have been emboldened to act without mercy. In his book "Nigeria and its Criminal Justice System" Farotimi Dele, exposes how the rich and the powerful individuals in Nigeria manipulate the justice system for their personal pecuniary interest (Dele, 2024). It demonstrates why the criminal system is toothless, weak and ineffective to tame corruption instead it fans the embers of the rich in society enmeshed in corruption. It is typical for the rich to get away with crime while Segun Olowookere, a poor boy at 17 years old got death sentence for stealing fowl (Uthman, 2024).. Corruption festers because the Nigeria criminal justice system is overwhelmingly engrossed in bribery and corruption. It shows the rottenness of the criminal justice

system and the reason why terrorism, insurgency, armed banditry, kidnapping and other violent crimes persist in Nigeria despite huge amount of money is voted every year for security.

Most studies (Transparency International Defence and Security, 2024; d'Agostino, Dunne & Pieroni, 2008; Gupta, de Mello & Sharon, 2001) on corruption and insecurity are based on the relationship between military expenditure and corruption and how it relates to security. For example, Transparency International Defence and Security (2024) examined the relationship military expenditure and corruption through the lens of defence governance and found that countries that spend more on defence as a percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) tend to score lower in gross domestic index (GDI) indicating a higher vulnerability to corruption. Corruption in defence and security were identified to include bribery, conflicts of interest, embezzlement, nepotism, and sextortion which undermines national development and security. Although, we are not dealing with military corruption per se but with the effect of corruption, criminal justice system and how the affect national development. However, the study findings are apt especially as they relate to corruption in general terms. d'Agostino, et al. (2008) examine the effect of corruption and military spending on economic growth and found that corruption and military burden lower the growth rate of gross domestic product (GDP) per capital income. Gupta et al. (2001) study found that corruption is associated with higher military spending as a share of both GDP and total government spending as well as with arms procurement in relation to GDP and total government spending. There is inadequate studies on corruption, insecurity and criminal justice system and how it impacts on national growth. Therefore, this paper is apt because Nigerians insecurity problem is rooted in corruption and criminal justice institutions inability to rise to their responsibility of justice delivery.

Theoretical Framework

The rational choice theory is adopted as the theoretical framework for the analysis of this study. The rational choice theory was first presented by Ronald V. Clarke and Derek B. Cornish in 1986. The main idea of the theory is that individuals will use decision making mechanisms to weigh options of benefits or otherwise of a crime before taking risk of committing the crime. In this respect, if the benefits of committing the crime are more than the risk involved, individuals are most likely to commit the crime. According to Tayler (1997, p. 293) "people will commit a crime if it is their own best interests". This means that if individuals perceive that there are more reasons for committing the crime, regardless of the existing security barriers, then at the very least moment an attempt will be made, if an opportunity presents itself, there is a benefit and there is little likelihood of being apprehended; then they will commit the crime. Clarke and Cornish (1985) argued that offenders seek to benefit themselves by their criminal behaviour by avoiding risks. Applying the theory to our study, it would be perceived that persons who engage in corrupt activities especially in financial crimes take calculative high risks because of the short and long term benefits the derive from their crime. In this respect, they know that the laws and penology on financial crimes are weak coupled with weak institutions of the state such as the judiciary and law enforcement agencies. They also rationally take the risk of stealing or embezzling public funds at their disposal because options abound that guarantee their personal interests are protected thereby assuaging the risk involved. Corruption is as high as the state institutions to meet out appropriate punishments for the crime. You can imagine a situation where a public servant embezzles over two billion Naira meant for buying of security equipment and when caught and prosecuted get a three year imprisonment while a poor man who steals twenty thousand Naira from a shopping mall gets seven years imprisonment. The allocation of punishment is disproportionate to the amount of money involved. In this situation, individuals would rather prefer to steal huge amount of money and less punishment than stealing just a little amount of money and getting more and severe punishment. Most pathetically is the fact that the institutions that are established to protect the citizens' rights and sanctity are enmeshed in corrupt practices; fighting crime through state established institutions become a herculean task in Nigeria. In this case, no matter how tight the target hardening are put in place to prevent corruption; individuals will dare the system because of the porous nature of combating the phenomenon. So the choice to take the risk to commit crime is solely at the decision of the offender irrespective of all odds.

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopts the exploratory research method of analysis basically relying on secondary sources such as the journals, books, statistics, periodicals and internet sources.

DISCUSSION

The Nexus between Corruption and Insecurity

Corruption is exhibited by individuals at different levels of position, occupation or status in various forms. The man in government position, in professional responsibility or in governance get themselves entangled in acts of corruption endangering the lives and property of citizens through their deliberate activities or negligence which has great devastating effect on security cum national development. The pervasiveness of corruption and insecurity in Nigeria greatly impact on the growth and development of the country; this is further worsened by the incapacity of the criminal justice institutions to deal with the duo effectively. Thus, Chinnah (2020, p. 70) lamented that “prebendalism, kletocracy, cronism, and nepotism have held Nigeria hostage at the cross road to development”. Corruption and insecurity are severe epidemics that need declaration of emergency in order to deal with it headstrong. Corruption not only facilitate insecurity, it’s the wing on which insecurity is sustained. Attempt is made here to outline some cases of corruption that have implications on insecurity and national development.

In 2014, a private jet was accosted in Johannesburg Airport, South Africa with the sum of \$15 Million US Dollars cash purported to be money for arms deal between Nigeria and South Africa (Agbakwuru & Erunke, 2015). This was a period Boko Haram saga was raging and some local governments in Borno State, North East, Nigeria had already been occupied by the terrorist group and their flags hoisted. The issue of kidnapping and other violent crimes were on the high side, yet this money was never investigated nor arms or military weapons bought to aid the combat of insecurity in Nigeria. More so, the former Army Chief of Staff, General Azubuike Ihejirika, the former Chief of Air Staff, Rear Admiral Minimah and 52 other military officers were indicted in arms panel involving #381 Million Naira for the procurement of military weapons to fight insecurity especially Boko Haram and kidnapping. The Panel also found that between 2007 and 2015 military contracts awarded were awarded to persons without technical knowledge and competence and without due process or contribution from the military (end users); while most of the contracts were fully paid there was no evidence that the arms or military equipment were bought or brought into Nigeria for military use ((Press Release, 2016). This impunity in government corruption and inability of criminal justice institutions to stem the tide provided the leverage for the escalation of insecurity in the country to the level that government security forces are overly overwhelmed by the activities of terrorist groups and organized kidnapper mafias in Nigeria.

In 2015, the former National Security Adviser, Col. Sambo Dasuki (Rtd.) was involved in arms scandal that has become known as ‘Dasukigate’. Col Sambo Dasuki (Rtd.) and other persons were alleged to have misappropriated over \$2 Billion US Dollars supposedly for the purchase of arms to combat insurgency, terrorism, kidnapping and other violent acts (Alli, 2015; Ayeotan, 2015). Though, Dasuki and some others were arrested and charged to court, but nothing tangible will come out of the case because it is a political vendetta in which the ruling government of All Progressive Congress (APC) want to use to keep their political opponents in constant control and check. In 2016, the Vice President Prof. Yomi Osibanjo alleged that the People Democratic Party (PDP) embezzled over \$15 Billion US Dollars public fund through fraudulent arms deals (Karuri, 2016). The Government responsibility to provide security and welfare for all citizens is severely jeopardized by her inability to contain corruption and insecurity through its inert actions or inactions.

In 2021, it was alleged that a citizen of Niger Republic Mr. Aboubakar Hima was paid about #166 Million Naira to supply military equipment for the Nigerian Army, but he never supplied those arms or supplied poor standard equipment (Sahara Reporter, 2021). Similarly, in 2020, an independent body (The Inspection Generale des Armes) that audited the armed forces found that out of \$875 Million US Dollars in military spending, \$320 Million Dollars was misappropriated. In addition, .much of the equipment were overpriced, not actually supplied and were awarded without due process (Anderson & Sharife,

2020). As if that is not enough, the National Security Adviser, General Babagana Monguno alleged that money allocated for the supply of arms and ammunition for the military under the past service chiefs namely General Gabriel Olonishakin (Chief of Defence Staff), General Tukur Buratai (Chief of Army Staff), Air Vice Marshall Abubakar Sadique (Chief of Air Staff) and Rear Admiral Ibok Ibas (Chief of Naval Staff) were not accounted for and there was no evidence on ground to show that the arms and ammunitions were purchased (Aytogo, 2021). In the midst of this arms scandal against the four generals, President Muhammadu Buhari retired them after severe pressure from the National Assembly and the public and went ahead to reward them with ambassadorial positions despite public protests. The implication is that overtly or covertly the generals are not alone in whatever action they took concerning the misappropriated defense money. Unfortunately, these actions have kept the country where it is in security index and by all standard the trend is not likely to abate in the near future unless subsequent government does something radical to change the narrative. Ironically, the government of President Buhari took power with the promise to improve security, combat corruption and enhance economic growth; but failed woefully. Unfortunately, the brazen attitude of the government illustrates that rather than fight corruption and insecurity they embolden those who engage in them. In sum, the Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) alleged that in the last two decades over #6.1 Trillion Naira was fraudulently embezzled through arms and ammunition procurement deals (Ogune, Musa, Abdulsalami, & Akomolafe, 2022). These explain why government and security forces are weakened and incapacitated in the fight against Boko Haram, terrorism, kidnapping, and other violent crimes thereby emboldening the capacity of violent extremists to feed fat in the vulnerability of the people. In a nutshell, the insecurity the country is facing today is as a result of government corrupt activities and inability of criminal justice institutions to checkmate it thereby reducing Nigeria's capacity in the development index. This is aptly shown in a report by ...that armed bandits and kidnappers had a net worth of over six trillion Naira as proceed of ransom payments. In fact, with this kind of money in the hands of terrorists, kidnappers and armed bandits government forces stand no chance to fight insecurity in Nigeria.

Aside from arms deal scandals and corruption which had impacted negatively on security, there are other areas in which individuals in government or security forces exhibit corrupt attitude that negatively impact on security. Nepotism in appointment and posting of military personnel could have great impact on security. Majority of military appointments by President Buhari were based on nepotism, religion and tribalism. Those occupying key positions in the military hierarchy either they are Muslim Fulani or Muslim Northerner. Unfortunately, the greatest problem of insecurity occurs in Northern Nigeria where majority of their people are in command positions. Fighting insecurity becomes impossible because some of those who are charged with the responsibility of counter-insurgency operations are either in sympathy with the terrorists or loyalists to the aims of the terrorists. In this regard, saboteurs within the ranks and files of the military frustrate every effort of effective military clampdown on terrorist groups. For example, the Boko Haram attacks on the Nigerian Defence Academy, Melete Military Base, Kaduna Airport and Kaduna-Abuja train track, Kuje Prison break have been attributed to linkages with insiders providing intelligence to the terrorists. It is the same reason many soldiers have been killed by terrorists who ambushed them on their way to Boko Haram camps and hideouts. The killing of a Brigadier General and four other soldiers by members of Islamic States of West Africa Province (ISWAP) at Bulguma, Askira Uba Local Government Area, Borno state in November 12, 2021 is illustrative. The soldiers were ambushed by ISWAP on their way to provide reinforcement for soldiers battling terrorists in the area (Omonobi, 2021). In the same vein, on February 24, 2022 soldiers who were on their way to fight terrorists in Maiduguri, Borno state were ambushed by Boko Haram and ISWAP and in the processes several soldiers were injured while others went missing (Sahara Reporter, 2022). There have been several incidents of this nature. The ambushes may not be unconnected with corruptions within the military which has incapacitated the ability of security forces in combating terrorism in Nigeria. In fact, the issue has worsened to the extent that patriotism and "Esprit de corps" no longer exists in the military; officers on insurgency or other field operations no longer join their men in combat operation neither do they

reveal their whereabouts to their men until the task is over. Officers are afraid to trust their lives to their men in field operations.

Lance Corporal Jibrin, a military instructor with the Nigerian Army Battalion in Geidam, Yobe State was one of those Boko Haram that attacked Geidam communities in Yobe state on 24 April, 2022. His arrest and confession led to the arrest of other military officers who joined Boko Haram to attack Geidam communities (Saleh, 2022). Fortunately, we have many of their types in the military and government. It was this fact that made President Goodluck Jonathan to lament the difficulty faced by his government in tackling Boko Haram was the reality that members of Boko Haram were in his government. There were in the legislature, executive, judiciary, the police and the armed forces. In the same vein, the Primate of the Anglican Communion Church of Nigeria, Most Rev. Nicholas Okoh, asserted that corruption and insecurity persisted in the country because the main people who supposed to fight terrorism lack patriotisms (Adetayo, 2012). In this kind of situation, fighting insecurity become a herculean task, perhaps that is the reason the menace of Boko Haram and other criminal elements have continued to succeed in their attacks. More so, Boko Haram was tolerated by Northern elites and politicians at the onset (Adefulu, 2011; Taiwo-Obalonye, 2011) because most of them felt it was paying back time for President Goodluck Jonathan. The military, the police and other para-military forces engaged in the internal security of the country involve themselves alike in various forms of corruption that undermine the security of the people. For instance, soldiers allegedly give firearms and ammunitions and also uniforms to criminal elements for disguise. Most of the herdsmen militia that attacked most places like Benue, Taraba, Kaduna, Plateau, Niger and other states are said to be in military uniform (Olayoku, 2014). Some men of the disbanded Special Anti-robbery Squad Lagos command are alleged to assist armed robbers to escape justice and also threaten the lives of victims who attempt to recover their items from the armed robbers (Onyecholem, 2001). Sometime in 2018, General T.Y. Danjuma, former Army Chief of Staff alleged that the armed forces were biased in their operations, they collude with armed bandits that kill people and kill Nigerians, secure their movement and protect them from arrest and prosecution (Obichie, 2018). Aside from these, men of unquestionable characters are consistently recruited into the security forces through corruption and these men are expected to fight crime. It is vital to note that recruitment of security men that is compromised and engrossed in corruption will definitely affect the turnout of those officers in terms of security maintenance and overall security provision in the country. It has also been alleged that members of Boko Haram who were granted amnesty were reintegrated into the military. Recently, 13 ex-boko haram members (known as hybrid forces) who were coopted into the joint military forces were said to have escaped with military rifles (Mohammed, 2024). Nigeria has become a game field in which systemic corruption have destroyed.

Challenges of Criminal Justice Institutions on Corruption and Insecurity

The criminal justice institutions responsible for the enforcement of laws and other processes in respect of corruption in Nigeria will include the Police, Court, Nigeria Correctional services, Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC), Directorate of State Services (DSS), Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC), and Code of Conduct Bureau (CDC). The focus of this section will be on the police, the court and EFCC in relation to arrest, investigation and prosecution of corrupt members of the society. The police and EFCC has the constitutional responsibility to arrest and prosecute any person found liable to financial crimes and other related offences while the court has the statutory jurisdiction of adjudicating such matters to determine the culpability of person brought before it. The actions of the tripod institutions to a great extent determines the quantum or tolerance level of corruption in the country. The three institutions serve as the societal pivotal wage and perhaps determines the direction, dimension and intensity of corruption based on their activities. The activities of these institutions will either impact positively or negatively on security. It will also determine to a very large extent the kind of security or insecurity that prevails in the country.

The 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria established for the independence of the three arms of government – the executive, legislature and judiciary for accountability, checks and balances to

enable a seamless governance. In practice, the institutions responsible for law making and adjudication have jettisoned their constitutional roles due to the crumbs they receive from the executive arm of government. This without mincing words has severely affected justice delivery and heightened insecurity cum corruption to the highest level.

The police, the court and the EFCC are rife with corruption to the extent that criminal elements trample on them while citizens wallow in failed corrupt institutions. The Police look the other way while criminals go on rampage and when they arrest; prosecution is poorly done due to lack of due process, diligent investigation, tampering of evidence or misappropriation of monetary evidence cum lack of investigative skills and training. The court that used to be the hope of the common man in terms of justice have lost its savor as justice is delivered based on the heaviness of your Ghana must go bag. A veiled justice no longer deliver justice veiled; justice must unveil to give justice because there is nothing like justice: injustice pervades the courts due to nepotism, political interference, socio-economic stations, ethno-religious sentiments, godfatherism, and financial pulse. No wonder criminals no longer revered to the court; the court is no longer a hallowed chamber: it is a place of injustice thereby exacerbating criminal impunity and insecurity in the country. The EFCC has become a tool for the oppression and suppression of political opponents of the ruling party. They have no need to arrest or interfere in the fraudulent and criminal activities of politicians in the ruling party and when they do; they do so on the basis of the more you look the less you because no meaningful outcome will be heard of such arrest. Most importantly, high profile corruption cases involving ex-governors, ex-senators and other government officials have been buried without trace and most of them that have been indicted and those who indicted them are now dining and winning together in government. Political interference, ethno-religious lineage, political party affiliation and pecuniary interests serve as the bane of the institutional failure in fighting corruption and checkmating criminality and insecurity in the country. The three institutions have abysmally failed Nigerians who fund their extravagant lifestyles. In return for their goodness to the three institutions, Nigerian citizens are degraded and taunted persistently due to insecurity with severe impact on national development.

Implications on National Development

The Nigerian economy is on the downturn. Poverty, unemployment, food security and general incapacity to socio-economic structures due majorly to misappropriation and corruption associated with governance. Money squandered or misused or diverted to private pockets would have been used to enhance the economic development for national development. Thus, national development is adversely affected due to insecurity truncated by myriad of corruption allegations which have remained unsolved. Insecurity have great impact on production, supply and distribution as farmers dare not go to farm due to Boko Haram insurgency and militia herdsman. National development is dwarfed as corrupt infested country cannot meet its developmental goals no matter how lofty the developmental policies may sound. This is exacerbated by a criminal justice institutions that are riddled by inefficient and ineffective justice system administration in which the lady justice blindfold has been unveiled thereby demystifying justice. No country, no matter how economically robust can survive a weakened justice system in which the rich blatantly oppress the weak through the instrument of corrupt law enforcement agencies and judicial system. National development is placed on the balance of the survival of the fittest as state of normlessness assume the national grid. Unpopular socio-political economic policies cum corruption breed insecurity already riddled by weak criminal justice system have severe implications on national development.

Corruption, weak justice system cum insecurity are opposed to local and foreign investments. How can a country grow its national economy without local and foreign investments? The trio are enemies of national development. National development thrives in the atmosphere of peace, stability, rule of law upheld by the justice system, security and corrupt free environment. Nigeria is abundantly blessed with natural resources, human capital, good climate, vast arable green lands etc. but insecurity, corruption and visionless rulers have messed up whatever good we have coupled with bad governance which has made

scholars (Barma, 2024; Dennis, 2023; Ibab, 2021; Anyanwu, 2005) to describe Nigeria as failed or failing state. Barma (2024) argues that a state that is unable to perform the two basic functions of the sovereign nation state in modern system such as inability to project authority over its territory and people and protect its national boundaries is a failed state. Nigerian citizens most likely no longer believe that their government is legitimate and that is why it has allowed illegitimate non-state actors to occupy its territory killing and destroying communities with impunity. This has crippled local and foreign investment and caused capital flight with grave implications on national development.

Nigeria is tagged the capital poverty of the world and this is made visible in the level of poverty, unemployment, diseases, corruption, lack of rule of laws, disrespect to human rights, and insecurity that pervades the entire landscape of Nigeria. Madhok and English (2023) noted that as of January 16, 2023, over 25 million Nigerian were said to be at risk of hunger particularly in Northern Nigeria where violence and insecurity had persisted. Hungry people, unemployed citizens, sick people and people crippled by fear of criminal victimization cannot contribute to the national development because they need help and support from government. Money embezzled through fictitious contracts and claims in arms deals could have been used to develop other sectors of the economy and secured the country but rather we have an economy that is totally weak and unproductive thereby creating multifaceted social problems. Most crucial is the fact that with its enormous natural resources, diverse economy cum strategic geopolitical position in Africa, Nigeria's national economic development has great significant implications not only for its citizens but also for regional global economic stability. This can only be possible if the country remains at peace to attract economic growth and development.

The country is witnessing great capital flight in terms of human capital and economic investment due to insecurity, corruption and weak judicial system. It is no longer news that many Nigerian professionals (medical and allied workers, engineers etc.) are leaving the country in droves while foreign companies are relocating to nearby African countries like Ghana and South Africa. In 2022 foreign direct investment inflow to Nigeria dropped by 33% about \$468.91 million which is considered the lowest in nine years (Punch Editorial Board, 2023) coupled with the dwindling free fall of Naira to Dollar at the foreign exchange market. Furthermore, the Minister of Finance, Mr. Wale Edun lamented that multinationals were leaving Nigeria due to problems in foreign exchange (Adeduyite, 2024). The implication is that national development is most likely going to be grossly affected by this narrative.

CONCLUSION

Corruption is dysfunctional in its entirety in human and societal development. National development is dwarfed by the heavy burden of corruption, insecurity and inefficient and ineffective criminal justice institutions ridden also by corruption, ineptitude, and impunity. Corruption is anti-thesis to what is morally upheld as acceptable value system in all human society, though functionalist (Durkheim, 1958) would ascribe to corruption even insecurity a functional status in society. It is held by many sane persons in Nigeria that country's insecurity problem is worsened by the level of massive impunity of corruption in governance especially in the way Boko Haram insurgency, armed bandits, herdsman militia and other terrorist groups have been cuddled in the last decade. The way government define problem will also determine the direction of their reaction, thus government seem to effectively define corruption, insecurity and incapacitated criminal justice institutions as acceptable frameworks of governance. The complicity demonstrated by government in the handling of insecurity (terrorists – Boko Haram, Islamic states of West African Province (ISWAP), Bandits, kidnappers, herdsman terrorism etc.) in the country is the degree and level of corruption in which they are enmeshed. Government politicization of corruption, insecurity and ineffective criminal justice institutions are smudge in national development. The fight against corruption and insecurity must not be peripheral, it must be deep rooted, holistic, and systematic with severe application of equity law devoid of all clouds of bias.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are suggested as ways of getting out of the deep rooted corruption in the polity and salvaging the country from insecurity and ineffective criminal justice institutions toward national development:

1. Government and its security agencies need to reclaim Nigeria from foreign invaders/mercenaries, kidnapers and terrorists and restore the hope people have on responsible government. National development can only be possible when peace thrive. Nigerian rulers must not push the country to that John Hobbs (1588-1679) state of nature which is solitary, poor, nasty, brutish and short.
2. Government must as a matter of national urgency and imperative revisit some of its unfavourable socio-political economic policies that have weakened the economic strength of its citizens in order to re-energize and empower citizens for national economic growth cum reduction in poverty and unemployment.
3. Nigerians must take the destiny of this country in their hands, they should no longer seat on the fence and allow political rulers to take the country for granted. Nigerians must wake and stand up to push out any government that projects unpopular political and economic policies that is anti-people and their welfare. Citizens can no longer watch their rulers' waste money uneconomically, corruptly and selfishly while the rest of the people lavish in abject and absolute poverty and starvation. The people must rise against unpopular government and restore the country from total collapse.
4. Government must be serious with governance and allow rule of law to guide its actions. Corruption festers because government benefits from it and pay lip service to it. Institutions especially the criminal justice institutions in Nigeria must be allowed to operate independently with minimal political interference to curb the bane of national development which is corruption. Therefore, justice must be allowed to rule our polity and those found corrupt in any form must not be allowed to participate in the country's politics. There is no country in the world that develops with weakened criminal justice institutions. It is time for the criminal justice institutions to rise up their constitutional responsibilities without bias for the country to develop like other climes.

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